

Enabling data discovery in big datasets

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Abstract. The ESAC Science Data Centre (ESDC) is handling the archive data for several astronomy, solar and planetary missions. We started with some gigabytes of information, currently in the hundreds of terabytes and not so far in the future we will handle with petabytes. Some important fraction of them reside in database systems which allows to analyse the data directly in the ESDC systems using VO protocols. All kinds of data: structured, semi and unstructured. How to store this data in a database to give the users the ability to query easily the contents of a space mission?. How do we choose a solution that will handle some small data to one that scales better for big data. May this be a nightmare? One does not fit all, but maybe in the future it well may happen.

We will review the evolution of database solutions for big data space projects with special focus in the ones that we have already tested (PostgreSQL, CitusDB, PostgresXL, Greenplum) with specific implementation for the Gaia DR3 release, the European JWST archive, the Euclid Science Archive and the future PLATO Data Archive.

1. Introduction

At the ESAC Science Data Centre the engineers and scientists work for creating the Astronomy, Planetary and Helio mission archives from ESA missions and the continuous challenge is how to work with the demanding big data volume issues. Traditionally the data belonging to a mission archive is divided in data located in a file system and catalogues and metadata stored in a database software provider system. The data could come at the end of a mission or just being part of the mission, collecting significant data that will serve scientists from the mission consortium first to analyze the mission data and later to the public. The structure of this archive system will depend on the requirements from the mission normally evolved from the continuous work between the archive scientists and the development teams from the archive group. But the challenge of the new archives is the big amount of data generated from the missions that must be offered in a quick and useful way to the scientists.

The work of the archives is to enable the data discovery for the different ESA missions to all the astronomers and interested persons. We care currently for 23 missions data from astronomy, planetary, helio and human and robotic exploration missions. Participating in the development, operations, post-ops and legacy phases to enable the

exploitation and visualization of the products, providing the data and the tools to try to make the work of the astronomers easier. All needs to be done in a cost-effective way as the caring should be thought on a long-term basis.

2. The archives

As the archives visible door is a web portal allowing the users to query the different archives, it is natural to store the metadata and catalogue data in a database for fast access to the data. The main website for the archives is: <http://archives.esac.esa.int>.

3. System stack

When the scientific data is ready it will be ingested on our databases (mainly metadata and/or catalogues) and if there is a data repository it will be stored in a petascale data storage then using VO protocols Dowler et al. (2011) the data will be able to be retrieved via a web portal, Jupyter notebooks or under the science exploitation platform Navarro, V. and others (2019).

4. Archives size

The systems storing the data had evolved tremendously to be stored first all data on a single machine and then, moved to Network Attached Storage systems and/or machines with local terabytes of Solid State Disks, some with flash memory included to enhance the performance in a significant way. The following graph (Figure 1), presents the size of each ESDC mission archive PostgreSQL database. The databases hold primarily metadata describing the scientific contents of the data stored in files repositories. It can be seen that most of our databases are less than 100G, then from Hubble mission archive it starts increasing and then Euclid Pasian et al. (2014) and then Gaia reaches 42TB currently.

Figure 2 shows the size of the archives in file system, the difference are if the products are stored into the database or not (as in planetary) if the telemetry is stored (as in Lisa Pathfinder) or if the products are stored inside the database as in Gaia. Depending on the archive it will be decided what will go into the database.

5. Some statistics for Gaia

On figure 3, statistics on the amount of data downloads over the months since 2016 is shown. It can be seen that there is hype to get the data as soon as it is made public. The peaks we get every time we have a release: DR1: September 2016, DR2: September 2018, eDR3: December 2019 and DR3: June 2022.

Typically this data is downloaded from a content data network (CDN) which is a server located in different parts of the world from where the data can be downloaded by proximity.

Besides the number of users is growing for every release, patterns are being studied currently, performing datamining to learn behaviour and learning what the users

Figure 1. Archives DB size

Figure 2. Archives file system size

searching for, what are the hot queries. The plot sums users downloading data through the archive UI and Astroquery via Jupyter Notebooks.

6. Database systems at ESDC

Currently the main database system used is an open source system, PostgreSQL, very popular in the scientific community with many contributors and which holds excellent extensions for spherical queries

Postgres or PostgreSQL has been proved as a key component of the ESA Archives allowing not only spherical queries but also the use of healpix, q3c and Postgis extensions for geographical indexing and analyzing time series data with timescaledb extension. High availability and fault tolerance is another advantage of this system.

Figure 3. Gaia data downloaded

Figure 4. Gaia active users

PostgreSQL is a RDBMS but as the data volume grows it can evolve in a scale out manner.

- Most archives: PostgreSQL:10.2 to 14.5
 - Open Source
 - Spherical queries (pg_sphere, q3c, healpix, postgis)
 - Professional companies support (that we do not use at our own risk)
 - Full control over your data and how you leverage it
 - The built-in support and expertise of a true, community-driven database
 - Flexibility to run PostgreSQL on all major operating systems and empower a range of applications, use cases and data types
- Euclid SAS: Greenplum

- Euclid DPS: Oracle
- ESASky, PSA (some functionalities): ElasticSearch
- Euclid Prototype: Spark Peloton et al. (2018)
- Import from Files, MySQL...

7. Relational databases

7.1. PROS

It can be thought that for big amounts of data it should be used a NON-sql database but we have certain reasons to use relational databases and the main reasons are that they are great for structure data that can be normalized into tables and relationships that will allow to run complex queries, RDBMS are transactionally secure which means that if I make a ingestion of a bunch of data, if it fails it will remove all the bunch and not only part. And of course the reliability as they have been used for many years.

7.2. CONS

The main cons for not using them will be that they need a schema definition so everything is well packaged so it does not allow to have the data distributed as it can be a book file. If there is any change to a field on a table, all the table is affected and also as the data is split in a number of tables, the data processing may be slow if there are many tables and of course it will be needed a expensive hardware if high performance is needed.

8. Size Matters

Because to accomplish the previous analysis we need to understand that size matters, we need to think about scalability. For that purpose we need to do a good analysis and requirements will be fundamental. Our queries performance must fulfill the requirements, not only reading but also on ingestion. We need to prepare a realistic data sample to study the performance of the different systems to measure. And then we will compare ingestion times, retrieving times, administration issues and problems that may arise.

9. Scaling Example

An example we ran was an study for distributing our databases to be prepared for the tsunami of data in Euclid and Gaia. We started in 2018 testing distributed databases for PostgreSQL. In that momnt in the market there existed 3 options for distributed PostgreSQL architecture for scaling out:

- 2nd Quadrant Postgres-XL
- CitusData
- OpenSource GreenPlum

9.1. Postgres-XL

Postgres-XL <http://www.postgres-xl.org> is a horizontally scalable open source SQL database cluster. It is a solution flexible enough to handle varying database workloads.

Connections to the distributed database are done based on a connection to one of the coordinators. Having several coordinators allows to parallelized ingestion and queries when using a connection manager such as HAProxy. The Global transaction manager keeps the logic for connecting the information between the datanodes. Several tests have been done with the KiDS dataset [6] using 1 single instance, 3, 6,10,16 and 25 nodes to show scalability for simple queries and aggregates functions.

9.2. CitusData

Citus <http://www.citusdata.com> is a distributed database that extends PostgreSQL, allowing you to continue using all the powerful PostgreSQL features while still scaling. The main difference with Postgres-XL is that it is an extension of PostgreSQL and not a fork so it can support other extensions such as foreign data wrappers, which are not supported on Postgres-XL so far. There is no GTM node as the logic resides on the master node. By default the master node is only one and it needs to be replicated in case the setup wants to benefit for parallel ingestion using several master nodes. The data shard factor can be increased (default is 1) to allow having replicas of the data in the worker nodes or data nodes, in the same way a High Distributed File System (HDFS) works.

9.3. Greenplum

Greenplum <http://www.greenplum.org> is a big data technology based on MPP architecture and the PostgreSQL open source database technology. It is a fork from PostgreSQL software. Starting in 2020 Pivotal was acquired by VMware and VMware continued to sponsor the Greenplum Database open source community as well as commercialize the technology under the brand name VMware Tanzu Greenplum.

9.3.1. Apache Spark

We tested also NOSQL system using Apache Spark <https://spark.apache.org> where we uploaded the flagship catalog in Parquet format. This is also a distributed parallel framework. The POC we ran was on 6 Virtual machines with 32GB RAM each, 8 cores an standalone mode and using Netapp (NFS) as storage With that we could run a count on 25s so it is in the range of sharded systems.

We used then later to test cone searches and xmatches AXS which was presented in ADASS 2018, although an error on the xmatching in the poles was found so we could not investigate further.

10. Conclusions

The evolution of the missions requires new investigation on data storage and management. A single option does not fit all cases and choosing the right one for each archive will be necessary. Scaling out is a must for the future archives and we want to continue relying on open source software. We are already using Greenplum for Euclid Scientific

archive and we will need to do it for Gaia with about 400TB in DR4. Euclid will also become big data with about 80TB/year inside the database. More tests will be needed to ensure high availability, robustness, and good performance for ingestion and querying. Time to administer the resources and support from the community and the provider is also a key factor. We have to get a balanced solution between hardware, software and human resources to fulfill the requirements for each mission.

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